

Porting the Striped Smith-Waterman Library to RISC-V via LLM-Driven Translation

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Abstract— Manually porting SIMD-optimized libraries across instruction set architectures is costly and error-prone, particularly when optimized kernels rely on architecture-specific idioms. We introduce a fully automated, two-phase LLM-driven pipeline for translating x86 SSE code to native RISC-V Vector (RVV) intrinsics. The first phase produces a functionally correct translation based on `sse2rvv` [1], while the second rewrites that translation to exploit RVV’s scalable vector-length model. Both phases use an iterative compile-fix loop in which the LLM relies exclusively on compiler and simulator feedback to detect and repair errors. We evaluate the pipeline on the Striped Smith-Waterman (SSW) library, a production-grade genomics kernel. Relative to a manually written naive Smith-Waterman baseline, Phase 1 achieves up to 21.7× speedup, showing that a compatibility-layer-guided translation strategy can serve as an effective foundation for cross-ISA porting. Spike [2] simulation confirms that the Phase 2 transformation remains functionally correct across vector lengths from 128 to 4096 bits. On our target platform with a 256-bit vector length, Phase 2 delivers a further 1.30× speedup. Overall, the fully automated pipeline achieves performance and correctness comparable to those of a manually optimized implementation developed by a human expert with AI assistance.

Keywords— RISC-V, Vector Extensions, SIMD Translation, Smith-Waterman, LLM, SSE2, `sse2rvv`.

I. INTRODUCTION

HIGH-PERFORMANCE software often relies on hand-optimised vector code to accelerate its most expensive kernels. In bioinformatics, for example, libraries and tools such as `Minimap2` [3], `Parasail` [4], and `SSW` [5] use Intel SSE2 and AVX2 intrinsics to achieve substantial speedups in sequence alignment. While effective, this approach tightly couples performance-critical code to a particular ISA, making portability increasingly difficult. This is especially relevant for RISC-V, whose Vector extension (RVV) [6] introduces a vector-length-agnostic programming model that differs significantly from the fixed-width SIMD model used by conventional ISA extensions.

Manually porting SIMD kernels is costly and requires more than replacing individual intrinsics: developers must often reformulate loop structures, memory-access patterns, and data layouts to exploit variable-length vectors efficiently. As a result, porting becomes a complex process that demands substantial expertise in the low-level details of both the source and target architectures.

In this work, we investigate the porting of the

SSW library, a production-grade genomics kernel, to RVV as a case study in translating fixed-width SIMD code to the RISC-V Vector extension. SSW is a particularly challenging target because its implementation of Farrar’s striped query-profile technique [7] is closely tied to x86 SSE2’s fixed-width 128-bit SIMD model.

Compatibility layers offer a partial solution. Projects such as `sse2neon` [8] and `sse2rvv` [1] provide drop-in headers that emulate SSE2 semantics on ARM NEON and RVV, respectively, enabling rapid functional porting while limiting exploitation of vector lengths beyond the original 128-bit width. However, for intrinsic-heavy libraries with complex data-flow patterns – such as Farrar’s striped Smith-Waterman implementation – these headers often require manual intervention, as not all SSE2 idioms have direct equivalents in the target ISA. Higher-level wrappers such as `SIMD Everywhere` (SIMDe) [9] and `Highway` [10] abstract across ISAs, but require non-trivial code refactoring and may not cover all intrinsic patterns used in legacy codebases.

Recent work has explored LLM-based approaches to code translation [11], including SIMD intrinsic migration. `IntrinTrans` [12] uses fine-tuned models to translate individual intrinsic calls from x86 to RVV, while Lin et al. [13] address the rewriting of Arm SVE intrinsics to RVV. These efforts demonstrate the feasibility of LLM-assisted intrinsic translation, but stop short of end-to-end library porting with integrated correctness validation.

In this paper, we present an *automated two-phase pipeline* that translates x86 SSE2 libraries to native, vector-length-agnostic RVV code using a lightweight LLM in a compiler-feedback loop. Phase 1 produces a functionally correct binary via the `sse2rvv.h` compatibility header; Phase 2 replaces the compatibility calls with native RVV intrinsics written in a vector-length-agnostic style to exploit the target architecture’s full vector length. Both phases are library-agnostic: the LLM resolves compilation and runtime errors using only compiler diagnostics and simulator feedback, without library-specific transformation rules.

We evaluate the pipeline on the SSW library and make the following contributions:

- A two-phase, LLM-driven translation method that decomposes the SSE2-to-RVV porting problem into two tractable sub-tasks, producing the same sequence-alignment output as the original across vector lengths from 128 to 4096 bits.
- An empirical evaluation showing that the Phase 1 translation delivers up to 21.7× speedup

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over a naive baseline, while Phase 2 adds a further $1.30\times$ on our 256-bit target platform.

- Evidence that the fully automated pipeline generates native RVV code of comparable quality to that produced by a human expert assisted by AI tools.

The complete translation pipeline and all resulting code are publicly available at <https://github.com/alexfez1010/riscv-translator>.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section II reviews the Smith-Waterman algorithm, the RISC-V Vector extension, and related work on SIMD portability. Section III describes the translation method. Section IV presents the experimental evaluation. Section V concludes and outlines directions for future work.

II. BACKGROUND

A. The Smith-Waterman algorithm

The Smith-Waterman (SW) algorithm [14] computes the optimal local alignment between two biological sequences. Given a query of length m and a reference of length n , it fills an $m \times n$ scoring matrix H using the recurrence

$$H_{i,j} = \max \begin{pmatrix} H_{i-1,j-1} + s_{i,j}, \\ H_{i-1,j} - d, \\ H_{i,j-1} - d \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $s_{i,j} = s(q_i, r_j)$ is the substitution score and d is the gap penalty. The algorithm guarantees an optimal local alignment but has $O(mn)$ time and space complexity, making SIMD acceleration essential for practical use in genomics pipelines [3].

Farrar [7] introduced the *striped* query-profile technique, which reorders the scoring matrix so that consecutive elements in a SIMD register correspond to residues separated by a fixed stride. This layout eliminates the data dependency along the diagonal that limits naive anti-diagonal vectorization, achieving a $6\times$ speedup over earlier SIMD implementations. The SSW library [5] builds on Farrar’s approach with SSE intrinsics and is deployed in production tools such as MOSAIK and TANGRAM.

B. RISC-V vector extensions

The RISC-V Vector Extension (RVV), ratified as version 1.0 in 2021 [6], adopts a *vector-length-agnostic* (VLA) execution model. Unlike fixed-width packed-SIMD ISAs such as x86 SSE (128 bits) and AVX2 (256 bits), RVV does not encode a vector width in the binary interface. Instead, software determines the active vector length dynamically. As a result, a single RVV binary can execute correctly across processors with different vector lengths, provided that the code is written in a truly VLA style.

Key architectural features of RVV that distinguish it from SSE include:

- **Vector-length-agnostic execution:** RVV code can execute correctly across implementations with different hardware vector lengths.

- **Predicated execution:** RVV provides mask-controlled operations, enabling efficient handling of conditional computation and loop tails.
- **Decoupled vector configuration:** Element width, active vector length, and register grouping are configured dynamically rather than being fixed by the ISA.
- **Flexible vector memory operations:** RVV supports unit-stride, strided, indexed, and segmented accesses.

Several groups have evaluated early RVV hardware for HPC workloads. Lee et al. [15] benchmarked the first commercially available RVV 1.0 boards, while Brown et al. [16] assessed the 64-core Sophon SG2042 for general-purpose computing. Vizcaíno et al. [17] studied the impact of long vector lengths on HPC kernels, confirming that VLEN-agnostic code scales effectively across different implementations.

C. SIMD portability approaches

Three main strategies exist for porting SIMD code across ISAs:

Drop-in compatibility headers.

sse2neon [8] maps SSE intrinsics to ARM NEON through a single header inclusion, and sse2rvv [1] does the same for RVV. These compatibility layers provide the shortest path to a working binary, but limit performance to the source ISA’s fixed 128-bit width, preventing effective use of wider target vectors. In addition, intrinsic-heavy codebases with complex data-flow patterns – especially those relying on data-layout optimizations tied to a specific SIMD width, such as the striped Smith-Waterman kernel – often require manual fixes to compile successfully through such layers.

Abstraction libraries.

Google’s Highway [10] and SIMD Everywhere (SIMDe) [9] provide portable APIs that map to native code on each platform. Highway targets VLA architectures explicitly and can generate efficient RVV code, but adopting it requires rewriting the source to use the library’s API – a non-trivial effort for large, intrinsic-heavy codebases.

Source-level rewriting. Lin et al. [13] propose an automated framework for rewriting Arm SVE intrinsics to RVV, addressing translation between two vector-length-agnostic ISAs. IntrinsicTrans [12] uses fine-tuned LLMs to translate individual x86 intrinsic calls to RVV equivalents. Our work differs in two key respects: (1) we target end-to-end library translation rather than isolated intrinsic substitution, and (2) we use a general-purpose LLM without fine-tuning, relying instead on compiler feedback to guide convergence through iterative refinement until the translation compiles and runs correctly.

D. LLMs for code translation

Large language models have shown strong performance on code translation tasks across high-level languages, but the low-level, ISA-specific nature of SIMD intrinsics poses additional challenges.

Pan et al. [11] systematically studied bugs introduced by LLMs during code translation, identifying semantic mismatches and silent correctness errors as the primary failure modes — precisely the risks that motivate our integrated validation pipeline.

Our approach mitigates these risks by treating the LLM as a *patch proposer* within a closed-loop system: every change is compiled, executed, and validated against a reference before acceptance. The LLM never operates in isolation; it receives concrete error messages and must resolve them to proceed. This design ensures that the final output is correct by construction, regardless of intermediate translation errors.

III. TRANSLATION METHOD

Porting the SSW library [5] from x86 to RISC-V poses a significant challenge: the core Smith-Waterman kernel is tightly coupled to SSE intrinsics, using operations such as saturating arithmetic (`_mm_adds_epu8`, `_mm_subs_epu8`), packed comparisons (`_mm_cmpgt_epi8`), and byte-level shuffles (`_mm_srli_si128`) that have no direct equivalents in RVV. A manual rewrite would require deep expertise in both the SSE and RISC-V Vector (RVV) instruction sets, together with detailed knowledge of the algorithm itself—Farrar’s striped query profile technique [7] organizes score vectors specifically to exploit 128-bit SIMD lanes.

We address this with a two-phase, LLM-driven pipeline that decomposes the problem into two tractable sub-tasks: (1) a semantics-preserving translation to a compatibility layer, and (2) an optimization pass that replaces the compatibility layer with native RVV intrinsics. Each phase is implemented as a *ReAct* agent [18], a framework that interleaves reasoning and acting in an iterative loop. In the *Reason* step, the LLM analyses the feedback from the previous iteration—compiler diagnostics, simulator traces, or output mismatches—and proposes a minimal code patch. In the *Act* step, the patch is applied and the resulting code is run through a two-stage validation chain (detailed in Section III-A) that ends with output comparison against the original Intel SSE reference. The pipeline is fully generic: the agent resolves errors using feedback alone, without any hardcoded, library-specific transformation rules.

A. Phase 1: SSE to `sse2rvv.h`

The goal of Phase 1 is to produce a functionally correct RISC-V binary that preserves the original 128-bit SSE semantics. It relies on `sse2rvv.h` [1], a drop-in compatibility header that maps SSE intrinsic functions to equivalent RVV operations at a fixed 128-bit vector width.

The translation proceeds in two steps: a deterministic pre-processing step followed by the ReAct loop.

Pre-processing.

All SSE header inclusions (`emmintrin.h`, `xmmintrin.h`) are systematically replaced with `#include "sse2rvv.h"`. This transformation

is entirely deterministic and requires no LLM involvement.

A critical constraint enforced throughout Phase 1 is the *16-byte rule*. Even when the underlying hardware provides vector registers wider than 128 bits, all `sse2rvv.h` operations must preserve SSE semantics and therefore process exactly 16 bytes. Without this constraint, the translated SSW library produced correct results on 128-bit vector implementations, but silently corrupted the scoring matrix on wider RVV implementations.

ReAct loop. After pre-processing, the ReAct agent takes over. In each iteration the agent first *reasons* about the feedback from the previous iteration (or the initial pre-processed source on the first iteration), then *acts* by proposing a minimal search-and-replace patch. Each proposed patch is syntactically validated before application; malformed patches are rejected with explanatory feedback that feeds the next Reason step. Once a valid patch is applied, the modified code is run through the two-stage validation chain that constitutes the Act step:

1. *Simulator validation.* The source is compiled for the `rv64gcv` target inside a Docker container equipped with the RISC-V GNU toolchain (`riscv64-unknown-elf-gcc` with `-O2`) and the resulting binary is executed under the Spike RISC-V ISA simulator [2] with the `pk64` proxy kernel. Compilation errors or runtime failures (segfaults, assertion failures, etc.) are fed back to the agent as the observation for the next Reason step.
2. *Hardware validation.* The source is compiled natively on the Banana Pi BPI-F3 [19], a RISC-V development board based on the SpacemiT K1 SoC [20] featuring an octa-core in-order processor with RVV 1.0 support and 256-bit vector units, and executed on the board. The output is compared record-by-record against a reference run of the original SSE code on an x86 host: for each aligned sequence pair, the target name, query name, optimal alignment score, strand orientation, target end position, and query end position are checked for exact equality. If compilation fails, execution fails, the number of output records differs, or any field in any record does not match, the specific diagnostics or mismatches become the observation for the next Reason step.

The two stages execute strictly in order; the chain stops at the first failure and the diagnostic output is returned to the agent. A stage that succeeded in a previous iteration may fail after a new patch, and in that case the agent receives the new failure feedback regardless of prior success. The loop terminates only when both stages pass in a single iteration, at which point Phase 1 is considered complete. A fixed iteration limit prevents unbounded execution.

B. Phase 2: Native RVV rewriting

Phase 1 produces functionally correct code, but each vector instruction remains effectively constrained to 16 bytes regardless of the target architecture. On processors with 256-bit or wider vector registers, this leaves vector capacity underutilized. Phase 2 rewrites the Phase 1 output into vector-length-agnostic native RVV code that scales with the hardware vector length.

Why a separate phase?

Early experiments showed that asking the LLM to simultaneously map SSE intrinsics and generalize the translation to wider vector configurations introduced too many degrees of freedom. The model failed to produce reliable translations, confusing SSE 128-bit lane semantics with full-width RVV operations and thus generating code that compiled but produced incorrect alignment scores. By constraining Phase 1 to preserve exact SSE semantics, we reduced the task to a tractable problem with clear success criteria. Phase 2 then starts from known-correct code and focuses on a single, well-defined objective: generalizing the translation to vector-length-agnostic RVV execution.

Vector-length-agnostic rewriting pipeline.

Phase 2 uses the same ReAct agent architecture, but with a different prompt and objective. The agent incrementally replaces `sse2rvv.h` wrapper calls with native `<riscv_vector.h>` intrinsics, processing the code in multiple passes. Each pass targets a subset of the remaining SSE calls and constitutes one ReAct iteration: the agent reasons about the current code, proposes a patch, and the patch is validated through the same two-stage Act chain as Phase 1—simulator validation (cross-compilation and Spike execution) followed by hardware validation (native compilation, execution, and record-by-record output comparison against the Intel SSE reference). As in Phase 1, if any stage in the chain fails, its diagnostic output feeds the next Reason step and the Act chain restarts from the first stage. The key difference from Phase 1 is the termination condition: the agent must explicitly signal that the rewriting is complete by emitting a sentinel token (`ALL_WIDENED`), indicating that no `sse2rvv.h` intrinsics remain in the source. The loop terminates only when the agent emits this token *and* both validation stages pass in the same iteration.

The resulting code is vector-length agnostic: it adapts to the hardware vector length at runtime and processes proportionally more data elements per instruction. On a machine with 256-bit vector registers, the rewritten code processes twice as many score-profile entries per iteration of the inner Smith-Waterman loop as the corresponding 128-bit version.

Figure 1 illustrates the complete ReAct pipeline with the two-stage validation chain used in both phases.

C. LLM configuration and cost

The ReAct agent is instantiated with the MiniMax-M2.7 model [21] accessed through the

Fig. 1: Overview of the two-phase ReAct pipeline. Each phase iterates a Reason–Act cycle with a two-stage validation chain: (1) simulator validation (cross-compilation and Spike execution) and (2) hardware validation (native compilation, execution, and output comparison against the x86 SSE reference). Phase 1 terminates when both stages pass; Phase 2 additionally requires the agent to signal that all compatibility calls have been replaced.

OpenRouter API. The sampling temperature is set to 0 to reduce output variability. All code changes are proposed exclusively through search-and-replace blocks, which are parsed by a dedicated module robust to whitespace variations, markdown fences, and other common LLM formatting artefacts.

Each phase typically requires 3–8 ReAct iterations. At approximately \$0.05 USD per phase, the total cost of a complete two-phase translation remains under \$0.10 USD, substantially lower than that of a fully manual porting effort.

D. Translation variants

The pipeline produces four distinct code variants, summarized in Table I.

Table I: Code variants produced by the translation pipeline.

Variant	Phase	Description
Naive	—	RVV baseline using wavefront parallelism
SSE→RVV	1	Uses <code>sse2rvv.h</code> at fixed 128-bit width
Native RVV (manual)	2	AI-assisted expert native RVV rewriting
Native RVV (auto)	2	Fully automated native RVV rewriting via the LLM pipeline

The naive variant serves as a lower bound: rather than translating the SSE code, it reimplements the Smith-Waterman algorithm from scratch using native RVV intrinsics with wavefront (anti-diagonal) parallelism, the simplest vectorization strategy for dynamic-programming kernels. It serves exclusively as a performance baseline for comparison.

The native RVV (manual) variant was produced by a human expert assisted by AI tools, starting from the Phase 1 output (SSE→RVV via `sse2rvv.h`) and tasked with replacing the compatibility layer with native RVV intrinsics. The expert had full access to the repository (source files, build system, test harness, and validation tools) and iteratively verified correctness at every step using the same infrastructure described in Section III-A. A comprehensive RVV intrinsics reference document was used to provide detailed documentation of the target instruction set. Comparing this variant against the fully automated Phase 2 output allows us to assess whether the lightweight pipeline matches the quality of expert-guided rewriting.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Case study: the SSW library

The Striped Smith-Waterman (SSW) library [5] implements the optimal local sequence alignment algorithm using SSE SIMD intrinsics. It employs Farrar’s striped query profile technique [7], which reorders the substitution scoring matrix to maximise data-level parallelism within fixed-width SIMD registers. The library is used in production genomics pipelines including the read mapper MOSAIK [22] and the structural variant caller TANGRAM [23], making it a representative target for SIMD translation.

The test harness aligns a fixed set of 100 short reads (54 bp each) against a single reference sequence of variable length, reporting the optimal alignment score, strand orientation, and target/query endpoint positions for each of the 100 alignments.

B. Experimental setup

Platform. All RISC-V benchmarks are executed on a Banana Pi BPI-F3 development board [19]

based on the RVA22 standard and the first commodity processor to support the RVV 1.0 vector extension and 256-bit vector registers, which integrates the SpacemiT K1 SoC [20], an octa-core X60 processor with an eight-stage dual-issue in-order pipeline. Its memory hierarchy is notably lean, lacking an L3 cache and relying on 32KB L1 caches per core with a shared 1MB L2 cache (divided into two 512KB banks). Equipped with up to 16GB of LPDDR4-2666, the system provides a peak bandwidth of 10.6 GB/s. Despite its modest throughput, the platform is distinguished by its high energy efficiency, operating with a TDP of 3-5W.

The benchmarks are compiled for the `rv64gc` target ISA. Code is compiled with Clang for the `riscv64-linux-gnu` target at `-O2`. The x86 reference runs are compiled with GCC at `-O2` and executed on an x86_64 host running Debian 12 with Linux kernel 6.1.0. Simulator-based validation uses Spike with configurable vector lengths ranging from 128 to 4096 bits.

Datasets. We use five reference sequences of increasing length (Table II) to exercise the translation under varying computational loads. Each reference file contains a single chromosomal region, ranging from approximately 1 000 to 10 000 000 base pairs, sourced from the SSW library’s own test suite. The query set is a separate file of 100 reads of 54 bp each; performance therefore scales with reference length while the query workload remains constant. The variation analysis across all code variants is performed using the `10k.fa` dataset as the standard workload, as it provides sufficient computational load to validate the correctness of the translation and it is quick enough to run for the validation needed.

Table II: Reference sequences used for benchmarking. Each file contains a single chromosomal region; the 100-read query set is shared across all experiments.

Reference	Role in evaluation
<code>1k.fa</code>	Startup overhead, small-scale
<code>10k.fa</code>	Standard workload, correctness
<code>100k.fa</code>	Medium-scale performance
<code>1M.fa</code>	Large-scale sustained throughput
<code>10M.fa</code>	Maximum-scale stress test

Methodology. Each combination of code variant (Section III-D) and dataset is executed 10 times on the RISC-V hardware. *Cell updates per second* (CUPS) is a commonly used performance measure in the Smith-Waterman scenario, because it removes the dependency on the particular sequences used for testing. A single cell update comprises the complete computation of one cell in matrix H , including all memory operations and the corresponding computation of the values in the E and F arrays. The GCUPS metric (billions of CUPS) is calculated as

$$\text{GCUPS} = \frac{m \times n}{t \times 10^9}, \quad (2)$$

where m and n are the lengths of the query and reference sequences, respectively, and t is the exe-

cution time of the alignment phase only. The timing is taken from the SSW test harness’s own internal measurement, so FASTA parsing and other file I/O are excluded; this isolates the cost of the sequence alignment kernel itself, which is the part affected by the SSE→RVV translation. We report mean, median, and standard deviation of GCUPS for each configuration. After every run, the output is validated against the x86 SSE reference using the same record-by-record comparison described in Section III-A: alignment scores, strand, target and query names, and endpoint positions must match exactly. Only experiments that pass correctness validation are recorded.

C. Speedup over the naive baseline

Figure 2 shows the speedup of the Phase 1 translation (SSE→RVV via `sse2rvv.h`) over the naive baseline. The SSE→RVV translation consistently outperforms the naive variant across all dataset sizes, from 17.2× on the smallest dataset (1k.fa) to 21.8× on 100k.fa.

Fig. 2: Speedup of the SSE→RVV translation over the naive baseline, computed from median GCUPS. The `sse2rvv.h` compatibility layer delivers up to 21.8× improvement.

Even on the smallest dataset (1k.fa), the translation achieves a 17.2× speedup, indicating that Farfar’s striped query profile technique exposes substantial data-level parallelism even at small scales. The advantage grows further with dataset size: on 100k.fa, the SSE→RVV translation reaches a median of 0.169 GCUPS, compared with 0.008 GCUPS for the naive variant. This confirms that even a 128-bit-constrained translation based on `sse2rvv.h` captures the essential data-level parallelism of the original SSE implementation.

D. Phase 2 gains

Figure 3 compares the two RVV native variants against the Phase 1 baseline.

The benefits of the Phase 2 transformation are already visible on the smallest dataset (1k.fa), yielding speedups of 1.25× for the manual version and 1.23× for the automated version, and grow consistently with dataset size:

- On 100k.fa, the manual Phase 2 version reaches 1.28× and the automated version 1.27×.

Fig. 3: Speedup of the native RVV variants over the SSE→RVV (`sse2rvv.h`) baseline, computed from median GCUPS. Both manual and automated rewriting achieve similar gains, reaching 1.30× on the 10M dataset.

- On 1M.fa, the manual Phase 2 version reaches 1.29× and the automated version 1.28×.
- On 10M.fa, the manual Phase 2 version reaches 1.30× and the automated version 1.28×, showing that the advantage of the Phase 2 transformation is sustained at larger input sizes.

Crucially, the automated Phase 2 output matches the performance of the expert-produced manual version to within 2%. This demonstrates that the lightweight automated LLM pipeline can produce native RVV code comparable to that of a human expert assisted by AI tools.

E. GCUPS throughput

Figure 4 presents the mean GCUPS throughput across all translated variants and datasets.

Fig. 4: Mean GCUPS throughput, with standard deviation error bars, for the three translated variants across all datasets. The native RVV variants consistently outperform the 128-bit baseline, especially on larger inputs.

On the 1M.fa dataset, the Phase 1 translation achieves a mean throughput of 0.167 GCUPS, whereas the Phase 2 variants reach 0.215 GCUPS (manual) and 0.212 GCUPS (auto). On the largest dataset (10M.fa), the Phase 1 baseline reaches 0.172 GCUPS, compared with 0.223 GCUPS (manual) and 0.221 GCUPS (auto) for the Phase 2 variants. While relative standard deviations indicate stable and reproducible performance, these results remain significantly below the throughput observed in x86-based architectures. This performance gap is primarily attributed to the memory-intensive nature of the Smith-Waterman algorithm, which is bottle-

necked by the SpacemiT K1’s constrained memory hierarchy. Specifically, the limited L1/L2 cache capacities and a modest peak main memory bandwidth of 10.6 GB/s hinder the SoC’s ability to sustain the high data-feed rates required for optimal vector execution [24].

F. GCUPS distribution

Figure 5 shows boxplots of the GCUPS distributions for the three translated variants, with individual measurements overlaid.

Several observations emerge from these distributions:

- On the `1k.fa` dataset, all three variants achieve similar throughput values (0.14–0.18 GCUPS), indicating that fixed overheads dominate at small scale.
- From `10k.fa` onward, the Phase 2 variants clearly separate from the SSE→RVV baseline, with the gap stabilizing at approximately 0.05 GCUPS.
- On `10M.fa`, the manual Phase 2 variant achieves a median of 0.223 GCUPS, compared with 0.172 GCUPS for the SSE→RVV baseline, corresponding to a 30% throughput improvement.
- From `100k.fa` onward, the manual Phase 2 variant exhibits the tightest distributions, indicating more consistent performance once fixed overheads are amortized. By contrast, on `1k.fa`, the SSE→RVV baseline shows the tightest distribution, again reflecting the dominance of fixed setup costs at small scales.

G. Scaling behavior

Figure 6 shows how GCUPS throughput scales with dataset size for all four code variants, including the naive baseline.

The naive variant achieves approximately 0.008 GCUPS regardless of dataset size, suggesting that its unoptimized scalar loop is limited by computation rather than memory bandwidth. The vectorized variants achieve higher throughput as dataset size increases: the SSE→RVV translation improves from 0.142 GCUPS on `1k.fa` to 0.172 GCUPS on `10M.fa` as the fixed overhead of alignment setup is amortized over a larger amount of computation. The Phase 2 variants follow the same trend at a higher throughput level, reaching 0.223 GCUPS (manual) and 0.221 GCUPS (auto) on `10M.fa`. This shows that the Phase 2 transformation improves not only absolute throughput but also performance at larger input sizes.

H. Correctness across vector lengths

To verify that the Phase 2 code is truly vector-length agnostic, we executed it under the Spike simulator at every power-of-two vector width from 128 to 4096 bits. At each configuration, the sequence-alignment output was validated against the original Intel SSE implementation running natively on x86 using the same field-level comparison described in

Section III-A. All six configurations (128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048, and 4096 bits) produced identical alignment results, confirming that the translation correctly handles width-dependent loop tiling, remainder elements, and scalable vector memory access patterns.

I. Translation cost and effort

The complete two-phase translation of the SSW library, from x86 SSE source to vector-length-agnostic native RVV code, required under \$0.10 USD in LLM API costs and completed within minutes. Phase 1 converged in 5 iterations, while Phase 2 required 7 iterations. By comparison, the manual Phase 2 implementation was produced by a human expert assisted by AI tools, requiring substantially more time and effort while yielding nearly identical performance (see Section IV-D).

V. CONCLUSIONS

Porting SIMD-optimized libraries across instruction set architectures has historically required either expensive manual rewriting by experts familiar with both ISAs or the use of compatibility layers that sacrifice performance by constraining execution to the source register width. This paper shows that LLMs, guided only by compiler and simulator feedback, can bridge this gap by translating a production genomics kernel from x86 SSE to native, vector-length-agnostic RISC-V Vector code while preserving the sequence alignment results of the original implementation.

The key insight is that decomposing the translation into two phases –first achieving functional correctness through a compatibility header, then generalizing the result to exploit the full hardware vector width – reduces the overall problem into sub-tasks that a general-purpose LLM can handle reliably within a closed-loop system. The Phase 1 translation already captures the essential data-level parallelism of the original SSE implementation, delivering up to $21.7\times$ speedup over a naive baseline. Phase 2 adds a further $1.30\times$ by removing the 128-bit bottleneck and producing code that remains correct across vector lengths from 128 to 4096 bits.

Perhaps most significantly, the fully automated pipeline achieves performance and correctness comparable to those of a manual Phase 2 implementation produced by a human expert assisted by AI tools. This suggests that, for structured translation tasks with clear correctness criteria, the combination of a lightweight LLM and a robust validation loop can match the effectiveness of expert-guided alternatives.

It is important to note, however, that the absolute performance gains observed on the SpacemiT K1 are partially bottlenecked by the SoC’s hardware constraints, specifically its lean memory hierarchy and modest 10.6 GB/s main memory bandwidth. In memory-intensive kernels such as Smith-Waterman, these limitations prevent the vector units from reaching their peak theoretical throughput. Nevertheless,

Fig. 5: GCUPS distributions for the three translated variants across all five datasets, with individual measurements shown as scatter points. The native RVV variants consistently achieve higher throughput, with performance differences becoming more apparent on the larger datasets.

Fig. 6: GCUPS scaling across dataset sizes for all four variants.

the significance of these results transcends the current hardware: by producing vector-length-agnostic code that scales seamlessly, this pipeline establishes a viable path for migrating mission-critical HPC libraries from legacy x86 codebases to the next generation of high-performance RISC-V processors. As upcoming RISC-V designs incorporate wider memory buses and deeper cache hierarchies, the LLM-generated code will be positioned to exploit those resources without further manual intervention.

More broadly, LLM-driven translation occupies a practical middle ground that was previously unavailable. Traditional translation of low-level SIMD code has largely been limited to pattern-matching approaches that cannot handle the semantic complexity of operations such as Farrar’s striped query profile, where algorithmic structure is tightly coupled to the source ISA’s register geometry. Fully manual porting, while capable of producing highly optimized code, demands scarce expertise and substantial engineering effort—particularly as the RISC-V ecosystem grows and the volume of x86 code requiring migration increases. The approach presented here shows that LLMs can bridge the semantic gap between fixed-width and vector-length-agnostic SIMD models, handling the restructuring of loop tiling, memory access patterns, and lane-dependent idioms that defeat simpler translation strategies.

Several directions remain open for future work. First, the success of the LLM-driven agentic pipeline suggests it could be extended to explore alternative

vectorization schemes beyond Farrar’s striped approach. Within the context of the Smith-Waterman algorithm, future iterations could evaluate the automated implementation of diagonal-based or v-parallel strategies to determine which algorithmic structure best aligns with RISC-V’s VLA model. Second, the pipeline should be evaluated on additional SIMD-intensive domains—such as image processing, cryptography, and signal processing—to assess its generality. Third, extending the approach to AVX2 and AVX-512 source code would broaden its applicability to a wider range of legacy x86 codebases. Finally, as high-performance RISC-V hardware with wider vector units and enhanced memory subsystems becomes available, real-hardware benchmarking beyond 256-bit vector widths will be essential to confirm that the generated code scales effectively in production HPC environments.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper has been partially funded by the EU (FEDER), the Spanish MINECO under grants PID2024-158311NB-I00 and PCI2024-162578-3 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by European Union “ERDF A way of making Europe” and the NextGenerationEU/PRT.

Additionally, Alejandro F. C. has been supported by a predoctoral research contract funded by Universidad Complutense de Madrid and Banco Santander.

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